

ROLE OF DIGESTATE LIQUID FRACTION IN THE MICROIRRIGATION SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT: The success of the use of wastewater in the irrigation depends on a wealth of factors. These include the amount of solids in the wastewater or its filtrate, the ability of the suspended material to form biofilms, the pressure of the water in the system, the type of filters and emitters, and age of the systems. Digestate from crop biomass and manure is increasingly being used, and its liquid fraction was indicated as a potential source for a wastewater irrigation. When used for irrigation purposes, information on the solid particles fractions, mostly salts, of these liquids in the irrigation systems are scarce. In case of low pressure (60 kPa) and low rate emitters (0.9 and 1.4 L h⁻¹ emitter⁻¹), high quality drip tapes showed a reduction of uniformity of distribution by 5.2 % on average depending on the activated sludge used as secondary effluent. In the present work, we studied the role of an increasing ratio between a hydrocyclone-filtered digestate liquid fraction and tap water on the performance of an irrigation system and water quality. Treatments included 3 dilution ratios (10 %, 25 %, and 50 % of total solution used for the irrigation) in contrast to tap water as control and measurements were taken at an hourly basis on an 8^h irrigation cycle, that simulates most of the irrigation cycles occurring in a broad range of crops. Hydrocyclone filtration scarcely affected the traits of the digestate liquid fraction used for the irrigation. Irrigation with hydrocyclone-filtered digestate liquid fraction injected in the system at 10 % and 25 % dilution did not affect the performance of the system nor the traits of the liquid fraction released by the emitters, whereas using 50 % dilution of the HF-DLF consisted in a lower amount of liquid released and of an increasing pH of the dilution.

Keywords: drip irrigation, hydrocyclone, digestate liquid fraction

1 INTRODUCTION

Irrigation with low-quality water and wastewater, was already proposed as a technique to mitigate the shortage of high-quality water [1,2]. The use of wastewater or filtrate of the liquid fractions of various wastes can increase the availability of water for agriculture.

However, its use may cause several problems on the irrigation systems. These include the clogging of the emitters [1], as well as the deposition of solid materials in the tanks or other parts of the irrigation system [3]. Drip systems allow the achievement of high irrigation efficiency in areas with high water demand and low water availability. In these systems, water pressure is usually below 200 kPa, and emitters have internal serpentine to compensate pressure loss along the line and potential fluctuations in the water pressure.

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systems are scarce. Such salts are likely to precipitate and, together with other suspended solids, can easily clog the emitters of a drip irrigation system by a fouling accumulation [10]. However, little information is available about the efficiency of many emitters when subjected to wastewater, especially when using the liquid fraction of the biomass-based digestate, as the solid fraction can contain high amounts of organic material [11]. The aim of the present study was thus to test the efficiency of a commercial emitter when injected with the liquid fraction of the effluent from an agricultural biogas unit previously treated with a hydrocyclone filtration system.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study areas

The study was conducted in February 2020 at the CREA-IT institute (45° 31' 21.9" N 9° 33' 54.9" E, Treviglio, Bergamo, Italy). The liquid digestate used was gathered from an anaerobic digestion plant, stored in a tank and filtered using a hydrocyclone filter (Alfaturbo Hydrocyclone Sand separator 2). The hydrocyclone filter was placed between a storage tank and the operating tank. Both tanks had a 1 m³ maximum volume. After the filtration, the filtered liquid was shaken once per day before the beginning of the tests (see below) by gently shaking the tank using a forklift truck. The storage of the liquid digestate before using it at the irrigation setup lasted for 8 days. A water pump of 0.75 kW power (Pedrollo company, model: JSWm 2CX, San Bonifacio, Verona, Italy) was used to pump the digestate liquid fraction in the irrigation system. The operating pressure was set to 0.2

MPa. Samples were taken from the non-filtered digestate liquid fraction (DLF), from the filter outlet and from the filtered DLF to determine dry matter content and pH. The filtrate dilution (FD) factor had four treatments: One control using freshwater and three filtrate dilutions (10%, 25%, and 50% of filtrate in freshwater). Each irrigation cycle lasted 8 h and samples were taken once per hour. The water pump used was set at 0.2 MPa operating pressure, and the irrigation tank was filled with 400 L of DLF. Before starting each test, three samples were collected from the irrigation tank to measure the dry matter and the pH of the solution. Within each irrigation cycle, the pump recycled part of the water or diluted HF-DLF into the tank to keep it mixed and avoid particle deposition. The irrigation system was organized by three polyethylene 1-m long dripper tubes (Stocker company N° 26085, Bozen, Italy), as replicates, with three emitters each. The dripper tubes used had 0.016 m of diameter (maximum design pressure 0.4 MPa) and were spaced 0.33 m each other. During the tests, the water or filtrate dropping from the tubes was collected in plastic flagons placed underneath each emitter (Figure 1). The flagons were weighted once per hour with a portable scale to calculate the water flow (g h^{-1}). At the time of weighting the turbidity and the temperature of the liquid were measured. The temperature of the water or DLF were measured in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using the DS18B20 digital thermometer. The turbidity of water or DLF were measured by using the turbidity sensor SKU:SEN0189 (Arduino, Ivrea, Italia), which was used as an indirect measurement of filtrate and water quality. In particular, the higher the sensor output, the lower the liquid NTU value. The manufacturer provide an output for pure water of $4.1 \pm 0.3\text{V}$ when temperature span from 10°C to 50°C . Integration of the temperature and turbidity systems was made according to [12]. Dry matter and moisture content of the samples were assessed by oven drying at 105°C until constant weight [13]. The pH of the samples was measured with no dilution by using a CRISON GLP21 pH-meter (Hach Lange Spain, S.L.U., Barcelona, Spain). Then, the samples of each emitter per line were mixed and a random composite subsample of 500 mL of liquid was taken. Thus 72 total samples of DLF released by each line were obtained. Dry matter of each subsample and its pH, following the methodology described above, were measured.

Figure 1: Design of the irrigation tests.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The native digestate liquid fraction used before the hydrocyclone filtering had a higher pH than the tap water used ($\text{pH} = 8.23$ vs. 7.84 , respectively) and such pH

slightly reduced after the hydrocyclone filtering. Information on the effect that the hydrocyclone filtering has on the pH of digestate liquid fraction and its total solids are scarce, nonetheless, centrifuge filtering was shown to have relatively high efficiency [14]. Hydrocyclone filtering, however, did not result in a reduction of the turbidity and such results could be due to the high total solid concentration in the DLF following incomplete filtering, as pointed by Guilayn et al. [14]. Indeed, in our study, the HFDFL showed a dry matter concentration of 16.0% (on a weight basis) and a $\text{pH} = 8.15$ soon after the filtration. These traits suggested a low quality fraction for drip irrigators according to the early classification by Nakayama and Bucks [1]. When subjected to the 200 kPa pressure of the present study, we found that the amount of water released in the control ranged from 3.07 L in the first hour and such an amount increased on average by the $1.9\% \text{ h}^{-1}$. Such variation were higher than those found by Bodole et al. [15]. The variation of the amount of HF-DLF each emitter released per hour also increased with time in the three dilution treatments ($0.5\text{--}0.9\% \text{ h}^{-1}$), but to a lesser extent compared to the control. In particular, the dilution at 10% and 25% released 1.9% and 3.5%, respectively, more HFDFL per cycle than the water released by the control, whereas the dilution at 50% released 4.9% less HF-DLF per cycle than the control. Besides, the differences between each HF-DLF dilution and control in the amount of water released per unit time declined with time. In addition, the 10% and 25% diluted HF-DLF did not likely consist in a strong occlusion of the emitters. This is consistent with the constant rate of the dry matter content of 10% and 25% HF-DLF and increasing rate of the dry matter content of the 50% HFDFL. When using the 50% dilution, 6.63% less HF-DLF was released, on average, if compared to the water released in the control or the HF-DLF in the 10% and 25% dilutions. In contrast to our study, Gamri et al. [16] found a strong reduction of the emitter performance with time and difference between the present and the one by Gamri et al. [16] experiment can be due to the higher pressure we used, which is two-fold compared to their study, and this occurred despite our HF-DLF had a solid concentration 2.3–9.8 fold higher than the synthetic wastewater composition used by Gamri et al. [16].

4 CONCLUSIONS

Irrigation with hydrocyclone-filtered digestate liquid fraction (HF-DLF) injected in the system at 10% and 25% dilution did not affect the performance of the system nor the traits of the liquid fraction released by the emitters, whereas using 50% dilution of the HF-DLF consisted in a lower amount of liquid released at increasing pH. In particular, HF-DLF dilution at 10%, 25%, and 50% consisted in +1.9%, +3.5, and -4.9% amount of liquid released compared to the control. This implies that that highly concentrated digestate liquid fractions, can pose problems for the functioning of the system and may have potentially harmful effects on soils with high pH. Nonetheless, the use of digestate liquid fractions for irrigation purposes may be a valuable option in those areas with a high amount of biogas plants and digestate production, such as various nations in Europe, America and Asia including USA, China, Germany, United Kingdom, Italy, and France [17,18]. The ability to use such

wastewaters with minimal impact on the irrigation system, and thus with reduced negative impacts due to the system maintenance and disposal. However, since the present is a short-term experiment, these results would require additional experiments with unfiltered liquid fractions.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Nakayama, F.; Bucks, D. Water quality in drip/trickle irrigation: A review. *Irrig. Sci.* 1991, *12*, 12, doi:10.1007/bf00190522.
- [2] Pereira, L.S.; Oweis, T.; Zairi, A. Irrigation management under water scarcity. *Agric. Water Manag.* 2002, *57*, 175-206, doi:10.1016/s0378-3774(02)00075-6.
- [3] Adin, A.; Sacks, M. Dripper-Clogging Factors in Wastewater Irrigation. *J. Irrig. Drain. Eng.* 1991, *117*, 813-826, doi:10.1061/(asce)0733-9437(1991)117:6(813).
- [4] Capra, A.; Scicolone, B. Emitter and filter tests for wastewater reuse by drip irrigation. *Agric. Water Manag.* 2004, *68*, 135-149, doi:10.1016/j.agwat.2004.03.005.
- [5] Ahmed, B.A.O.; Yamamoto, T.; Fujiyama, H.; Miyamoto, K. Assessment of emitter discharge in microirrigation system as affected by polluted water. *Irrig. Drain. Syst.* 2007, *21*, 97-107, doi:10.1007/s10795-007-9022-6.
- [6] Goyal, M.R. *Wastewater Management for Irrigation*; Goyal, M.R., Tripathi, V.K., Eds.; Apple Academic Press & CRC press: Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2016; ISBN 9780429152498.
- [7] Puig-Bargués, J.; Arbat, G.; Elbana, M.; Duran-Ros, M.; Barragan, J.; De Cartagena, F.R.; Lamm, F. Effect of flushing frequency on emitter clogging in microirrigation with effluents. *Agric. Water Manag.* 2010, *97*, 883-891, doi:10.1016/j.agwat.2010.01.019.
- [8] Hills, D.J.; Brenes, M.J. Microirrigation of Wastewater Effluent Using Drip Tape. *Appl. Eng. Agric.* 2001, *17*, 17, doi:10.13031/2013.6215.
- [9] Makádi, M.; Tomcsik, A.; Orosz, V. Digestate: A New Nutrient Source—Review. *Biogas* 2012, 1-17, doi:10.5772/31355.
- [10] Green, O.; Katz, S.; Tarchitzky, J.; Chen, Y. Formation and prevention of biofilm and mineral precipitate clogging in drip irrigation systems applying treated wastewater. *Irrig. Sci.* 2018, *36*, 257-270, doi:10.1007/s00271-018-0581-0.
- [11] Akhiar, A.; Battimelli, A.; Torrijos, M.; Carrere, H. Comprehensive characterization of the liquid fraction of digestates from full-scale anaerobic co-digestion. *Waste Manag.* 2017, *59*, 118-128, doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2016.11.005.
- [12] Tahir, M.U.; Ahsan, S.M.; Arif, S.M.; Abdullah, M. GSM Based Advanced Water Quality Monitoring System Powered by Solar Photovoltaic System. In Proceedings of the 2018 Australasian Universities Power Engineering Conference (AUPEC), Auckland, New Zealand, 27-30 November 2018; pp. 1-5.
- [13] Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater. In Proceedings of the AWRA's 1999 Annual Water Resources Conference: Watershed Management to Protect Declining Species, Seattle, WA, US, 5-9 December 1999; APHA: Washington, DC, USA, 1999.
- [14] Guilayn, F.; Jimenez, J.; Rouez, M.; Crest, M.; Patureau, D. Digestate mechanical separation: Efficiency profiles based on anaerobic digestion feedstock and equipment choice. *Bioresour. Technol.* 2019, *274*, 180-189, doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2018.11.090.
- [15] Bodole, C.; Koech, R.; Pezzaniti, D. Laboratory evaluation of dripper performance. *Flow Meas. Instrum.* 2016, *50*, 261-268, doi:10.1016/j.flowmeasinst.2016.07.012.
- [16] Gamri, S.; Soric, A.; Tomas, S.; Molle, B.; Roche, N. Biofilm development in micro-irrigation emitters for wastewater reuse. *Irrig. Sci.* 2013, *32*, 77-85, doi:10.1007/s00271-013-0414-0.
- [17] Deng, Y.; Xu, J.; Liu, Y.; Mancl, K. Biogas as a sustainable energy source in China: Regional development strategy application and decision making. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 2014, *35*, 294-303, doi:10.1016/j.rser.2014.04.031.
- [18] Akhiar, A. Characterization of Liquid Fraction of Digestates after Solid-Liquid Separation from Anaerobic Co-Digestion Plants. Ph.D. Thesis, Université Montpellier, Montpellier, France, 2017. Submitted 15/01/2018 (NNT: 2017MONTS004).

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